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MATERIALS &
MANUFACTURING
RESEARCH GROUP

Electrical impedance tomography for self-sensing 3D printed cellular composites

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Outline

- Introduction
- Background and motivation
- Objectives of the work
- Algorithmic design of cellular structures
- EIT- computational exploration
- EIT- experimental results
- Conclusions and ongoing work

Cellular structures

- Achieve unprecedented properties by carefully structuring the building blocks
- Tunable mechanical/thermal/electrical properties
- Easily manufactured using 3D printing

[1] J U Surjadi et al., *Nat. Mater.*, 2025

[2] J. Schneider et al., *Adv. Eng. Mater.*, 2024

[3] J. Schneider et al., *Mater. Horiz.*, 2025

High stiffness and strength

[1]

Truss

TPMS

Fractal

Origami/kirigami

Tensegrity

Plate

Spinodal

Auxetic

Hybrid

Multimaterial

High energy absorption

High compliance and extensibility

Woven

Helical

Self-sensing composites via piezoresistivity

- Polymers, when loaded with electrically conductive nanofillers like carbon nanotubes, unlock multifunctionality
- Material itself senses strain/damage via stimuli-responsive behaviour: Self-sensing

[4] P. Verma et al., *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces.*, 2022

Electrical Impedance Tomography (EIT)

- Reconstructs domain's **conductivity map** from boundary voltage measurements
- Inverse problem
- Models the physics of electric passage
- Soft-field tomographic method

[5]

[5] K. Park et al, *Sci. Robot.*, 2022

Red Line: Current flow line

Blue: Equipotential line of the resulting voltage

Objectives of the work

- Geometric modelling and 3D printing of cellular composites
- Improving the spatial resolution in EIT image reconstruction by programming the Jacobian via lattices
- Computational and experimental demonstration of EIT for damage detection and localisation in cellular composites

Algorithmic design of cellular structures

(a) $S = T \cup \bigcup_{k=1}^4 B_k$

(b) $S_{i,j} = R_{\theta_{i,j}} + iT_x + jT_y$

(c) $V(P) = \{Q \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid d(Q,P) \leq d(Q,P'), \forall P' \neq P\}$

(d) $U(S_{i,j}) = \bigcup_{P \in S_{i,j}} V(P)$

(e) $U'_i = C + \alpha(U_i - C)$

(f) $\Lambda = U'_i \setminus Q$

(g) $\mathcal{L} = \bigcup_{i,j} \Lambda + iL + jL$

(h) $\mathcal{L}_3 = \{(x,y,z) \mid (x,y) \in \mathcal{L}, 0 \leq z \leq h\}$

*J. Schneider et al., *Addit. Manuf.*, 2024

*J. Schneider et al., *Mater. Horiz.*, 2025

EIT- Experimental measurement schemes

- Domain lined up with electrodes
- Current injected b/w first elec pair; voltages measured between remaining pairs
- Current injection moved to next electrode pair, and voltages measured again

First injection

Second injection

Last injection

Forward and inverse problems in EIT

Forward Problem

- Domain conductivity \longrightarrow Boundary voltages (using FE)
- Simulates physics of steady-state electrical current flow

Laplace's equation: $\nabla \cdot \sigma \nabla \phi = 0$

σ : Conductivity distribution
 ϕ : Domain potential

Apply complete electrode model boundary condition & charge conservation law

- Jacobian, $J = \frac{\partial V}{\partial \sigma}$,

Inverse Problem

- **Conductivity change**: minimizes difference b/w predicted and measured boundary voltages
- Ill-posed as J is ill-conditioned
- Requires regularisation

Programming Jacobian using Engineered lattice

- Existing approaches improving J include:
 - Increasing number of electrodes^[6]
 - Optimising electrode placements and measurement schemes^[7]

- Our approach:

Engineered lattice-based domains to improve J conditioning from within

- Calculate Jacobian (J) for each lattice
- Sensitivity = $[\|j_1\|_2/N, \|j_2\|_2/N \dots]$
where N = number of measurements

[6] M Tang et al., *Physiol. Meas.*, 2002

[7] D Smyl et al., *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, 2020

Computational exploration

- Undamaged FE domain
- Computing V_i via forward model
- Adding noise to V_i

(ΔV) *Computational*

- Damaged FE domain
- Computing V_f via forward model
- Adding noise to V_f

Solving
Inverse
problem

Experimental results

I

I: Intact PEEK/CNT cellular composite;

II

II: Damaged specimen at two distinct positions;

III: Corresponding EIT images

III

0.6

0.4

0.2

0

-0.2

-0.4

-0.6

-0.8

-1

Normalized Conductivity change

Conductivity loss overlaps with location of damage

Conclusions and ongoing work

- **Fabricated architected composite** lattice using nano-engineered PEEK-based filament via AM
- **Engineered lattice geometry** to improve conditioning of inverse problem- reducing null spaces & increasing distinguishability
- Conductivity maps show **precise detection and localisation of damage**
- Ongoing work involves *in situ* EIT applied to AM-based cellular composites

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Thank you.

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Collaboration

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